

THE USAGE OF INDIAN HOME REMEDIES IN A WESTERN-DOMINATED
SOCIETY

by

Ritika Kumar

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4480-2254

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Approved by:

Dr. Sapna Chopra, Department of Human Services

Dr. Yuying Tsong, Director University Honors Program

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“The Usage of Indian Home Remedies in a Western-Dominated Society”

The project I have been working on aimed to explore the beliefs about Indian home remedies and western medicine among Indian immigrants prior to immigration and post immigration. Being a second-generation Indian American and a child to immigrant parents, this topic is personally important to me because I grew up using home remedies that have been passed down from older generations in India. Given this history of generational knowledge, it is interesting to see how western medicine is centered mainly around drug therapy. Being the first generation in my family that has grown up using both western medicine as well as Indian Ayurvedic techniques- it has become important to me to understand what role such homeopathic healing plays in western society among Indian Americans who have migrated here from their homeland.

Ayurvedic technique is a widely used practice in India and is now emerging as alternative medicine in other parts of the world, such as in the United States. The traditional Ayurvedic system of medicine has been used for ages in India, dating back to scriptures in the Vedas. Ayurvedic technique derives from herbs, minerals, and organic matter, making it a form of homeopathic healing, an alternative form of medicine that strays away from western medicine (Pandey et al., 2013). Maintaining a healthy diet is deemed important in Ayurvedic medicine; rich nutrient foods allow for protection against infectious diseases, asthma, allergies, and other chronic illnesses such as heart diseases and cancer (Pandey et al., 2013).

Pharmaceutical industries have been working towards using herbs found in Ayurvedic technique to develop drugs derived from natural products. Ayurvedic medicine, according to Patwardhan, has gained more attention in the United States because it is taking up the form of drugs- which is what Americans more commonly associate with medicine. In developing countries, many individuals rely on Ayurvedic technique instead of modern allopathic drugs due

to its low-cost and effective mechanisms (Patwardhan, 2004). For that reason, as Ayurvedic technique is making its way towards United States, practitioners ensure to maintain the low cost when formulating herbs in a drug-like form, something that the U.S. healthcare system relies heavily on. Natural product discovery is research for future medicine; it will reduce time, money, and toxicity which are the most common forms of hurdles faced in drug development (Patwardhan, 2004).

Another perspective around Ayurvedic technique explains that Ayurvedic technique is a metaphysical system of healing and has grown popularity in the West due to millennial interests of homeopathic healing (Reddy, 2002). In the New age healing system, with millennials challenging common forms of medicine such as what is prominent in western medicine, Ayurvedic healing has become more accepted. Reddy argues that with an increase in spirituality among the new generation in America, higher levels of Ayurvedic professionals are gaining awareness among new age millennials. However, when publicizing Ayurvedic techniques in the West, practitioners try to emulate the western behavior while also trying to retain its Ayurvedic qualities (Reddy, 2002).

Gaining wide acceptance towards homeopathic healing methods through Ayurvedic technique becomes difficult when the public perception in the U.S. has been mainstreamed versions of Ayurveda such as yoga and a vegetarian diet (Park et al., 2012). The restrictive western mindset is centered on science, data, and research. Therefore, the lack of publication of the benefits of Ayurvedic medicine, lack of quality standards, and fear of Ayurvedic herbal medicine containing toxins minimize the widespread information of Ayurvedic technique reaching the western systems (Park et al., 2012).

Methods

Participants

To conduct the research, I interviewed six participants who are Indian American. The participants were purposefully selected based on their life experiences with both traditional Indian healing practices and western medicine; the participants were all family members of the researcher. Two age ranges were present: three participants that migrated around the age 10 and three participants that migrated after the age 50. Participants that migrated around the age of 10 were Amit Kumar (Male; age 40), Sumit Kumar (Male; age 39), and Komal Kumar (Female; age 38). Those who migrated after the age of 50 were Kamla Devi (Female; age 85), Bhimsen Munjal (Male; age 72), and Veena Munjal (Female; age 57). All participants gave permission to use their names and pictures for this project.

Procedure

Participants were selected based on their age of migration to the U.S. and prior knowledge around Ayurvedic techniques. Other factors noted were socioeconomic class and education status, which helped me later make sense of the project. Each participant was interviewed for about 20-30 minutes in their homes and was asked the same set of questions that were developed by the researcher. With the permission of the participants, the interviews were recorded and later transcribed. The questions asked were:

- What are the Indian remedies/treatments you grew up using?
- Can you remember how many times you got sick? What was your food intake, weather of location, and lifestyle like? After you came to America, how often did you get sick?
- What were your experiences with visiting a doctor in India? How often and what are the reasons?

- What Indian remedies do you continue to use living in the U.S.?
- Under what circumstances would you use Indian home remedies and which circumstances would you use western medicine?
- How have you incorporated these Indian practices into your family's lifestyle?
- What influence does your family have on using Indian/western medicine?

Data Analysis

Familiarizing myself with the data through transcriptions of the interviews became the first step in making sense of my findings. While transcribing, I made a separate document where I recorded the initial patterns seen with each interview. Once transcriptions for each interview was finished, I began to read and re-read through the interviews. I highlighted important phrases and concepts found in the transcripts and continued to add onto my own notes. Through this process, I identified themes that emerged from the interview data. I discussed my findings with my mentor who is also familiar with both traditional Indian practices and western medicine. My mentor read through my transcriptions to ensure that there were not missing information or misinterpretations of the data. Through her expertise, three themes emerged from my participants' interviews.

Results

Theme 1: Indian home remedies are learnt within Indian cultures and are passed down through generations.

The first theme was that Indian home remedies are learnt within Indian cultures and are passed down through generations. Veena Munjal mentioned, "The people in India know everything. the information comes from people on the streets who are knowledgeable about them. Over here, you can't ask the people at the supermarkets for such things." Similarly, Sumit

Kumar mentioned, “If there’s no science or research to give you some kind of data, then it has to be Southern. Because they were thinking’s and advice passed down from older generations.”

Some common home remedies shared by all participants were: turmeric, cloves, ginger, bilwadi churna, yogurt, shikakai leaves, and fennel seeds. Many of these common home remedies contain antioxidants that help to fight infection and disease. When asked how my they knew about these Indian home remedies, all the participants said they learnt it from India or from their family. Healing through foods and other home remedies has been imbedded into the Indian society, which is what binds that community together in a way. It is rooted in tradition and religion, gurus teach society medicinal properties found in leaves, herbs, spices. That information gets passed down to parents, which in-turn gets passed down to children. Indian home remedies are embedded in India’s society due to the high amounts of poverty present within the country.

There is not much money to go to the doctors and receive western treatment; therefore, residents are forced to figure it out on their own. Residents learn from shop owners on the streets, learn from parents, and learn from grandparents. Parents teach their children at a young age and therefore, the emergence of understanding the Indian home remedies becomes a norm. Now as the child grows up and has children of their own, it becomes time to teach their own children.

The cost preparing Indian home remedies are often done in a home setting and are used predominately in developing countries, such as India, due to their low cost and high efficacy.

Theme 2: Indian home remedies are a method for preventative measures, while western medicine is used for reactive measures.

The second theme was that participants felt that Indian home remedies are a method for preventative measures, while western medicine is used for reactive measures. As Kamla Devi mentioned during her interview, “Yeah. Starting, we try to use Indian home remedies. Like

ginger, honey, and salt. But if it gets worse, then we go to doctors.” There was a consensus between all my participants that Indian home remedies are used as preventative measures such as herbs and spices utilized in food, as well as prioritized in the beginning of sickness with eating ginger to reduce inflammation and fill the body with antibacterial to fight infections. However, when and if the sickness got worse, participants claimed they go to the doctors for instant relief in the form of pills. The huge difference between such Indian home remedies and western medicine is that many of these Indian home remedies are simply herbs, spices, and variations of foods to heal and prevent the body from diseases and infection. Western medicine, on the other hand, is the treatment of diseases and infection using drug therapy and is administered in a hospital or doctor’s office setting; it is used for instant relief. For example, if severe pain is felt, using drug therapy might help reduce the pain due to chemical reactions that will occur to instantly block the pain receptors. Western medicine is rooted in advances in technology through research, data, and statistics. Hospitals utilize drug therapy for instant relief for their patients. This is generally the case due to the relatively short-term stays at hospitals.

Theme 3: Healthcare professionals in both India and Western Society do not explain patient’s conditions; patients are left to explore their own conditions through their own knowledge.

The last theme I noticed within my participants was their belief that healthcare professionals in both India and western Society do not explain patient’s conditions; patients are left to explore their own conditions through their own knowledge. As Amit Kumar mentioned, “The patient should be self-educated enough to take care of themselves.” Most individuals I interviewed had a pre-existing condition, such as Crohn’s disease or asthma. Two individuals that both had Crohn’s disease explained that they had to self-educate themselves on their

condition and had to rely on themselves to lessen the severity of their disease. They were forced to navigate through society with their own knowledge. They expressed a lack of return towards their health care professionals due to the minimal information provided by such health care professionals. Increase in spread of information via technology leads to better access to information about patients' conditions; however, readmission risks are still high because there is no guarantee individuals will follow up with their own conditions. When health care professionals fail to inform patients about their conditions and steps to take, the distrust and readmission cycle continues.

Discussion

Based on interviews with six Asian Indian immigrants living in the United States, this study found that Indian home remedies are passed down generationally and are typically used for prevention of health problems, and that healthcare providers often do not provide adequate information to patients. The findings of this research offer important implications for healthcare providers. Multicultural training is needed for nurses, doctors, and anyone who works in the healthcare setting. Cultural humility, the acknowledgment that learning is an ongoing process and the lifelong commitment to attempt to learn other's cultures can be considered a form of multicultural training (Tervalon & Murray-Garcia, 1998). One way to develop cultural humility is through the process of first identifying one's own cultural background and identities. Self-awareness and respect towards culture also includes understanding other's cultures. Integrating both western Medicine and home remedies would allow care for the whole person. Most cultural groups have home remedies that they use that are different than western medicine. For that reason, relationship building between the health care providers and patients would allow a safe space for a conversation to be discussed about different home remedies that a patient uses.

Breaking the cycle of prioritizing the dominant western medicine is essential, especially when there are many cultures that reside in the western society. In addition, it is important that healthcare providers take the time to explain and answer patients' questions, as the participants in this study indicated they were often left to research on their own.

Efforts to commodify Indian home remedies have been made through pharmaceutical industries working towards using herbs found in Ayurvedic technique to derive natural products into drugs form. However, without fully understanding the roots behind the herbs and Ayurvedic medicine, western pharmaceutical industries have been capitalizing on the recent popularities surrounding the mainstreamed version of Ayurvedic technique. This would include yoga and the vegetarian diet. To be culturally sensitive and avoid cultural appropriation, it would be helpful for western scientists to study and honor the cultural origins of these ancient healing traditions in their research and practice. This research project highlights the benefits of listening to people's experiences with traditional healing practices and western medicine to better inform treatment.

Conducting this research on Indian home remedies and its role in a western-dominated society allowed me to personally explore the significance of Ayurvedic technique. Through this project, I was able to understand the role of homeopathic healing and how it is still important for my family, regardless of their migration away from their homeland. However, because the participants were the first people of my extended families to make it out into the United States, I was fascinated to see how true they hold to their Indian home remedies, while also using the benefits of western medicine to be the healthiest versions of themselves. As a future nurse, I aim to use the information I learnt throughout the project into practice by understanding the usage of home remedies in many cultural groups and how that may influence their overall health. I hope to use my current knowledge surrounding home remedies into practice by listening with intent to

my patients and embracing their individual cultures to develop my own sense of multicultural information.

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